

Good practices for workers in mushroom cultivation

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Author:

CTICH - Mushroom Technological Research Center of La Rioja, Spain (Project Coordinator)

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The problem

Many of the pests and diseases that can be found in mushroom cultivation could be avoided, as the spread and incidence of these pests and diseases are often due to human factors.

The solution

Training workers who are in direct contact with the crop is essential to make them aware of the importance of cleanliness, hygiene and correct management of diseases and pests that can be found in the crop.

Also, proper signage of work areas, highlighting the importance of clothing (gloves, hats) that is essential to wear in these areas and the use of disinfectant tools (disinfectant mats, hand disinfectant), is very important.

Benefits

A well-trained worker in mushroom crop management will help to reduce the incidence of diseases and pests, which makes mushroom cultivation more profitable.

Good practices of workers in mushroom cultivation

Practical recommendations

- Always go from the newest crop to the oldest one.
- Before entering the cultivation room use the disinfectant mat to remove contaminants from footwear.
- If working with substrate, peat or mushroom; always wear gloves.
- If you have been working in a room with disease and/or pests, change your clothes when you leave and disinfect them before their next use.
- Workers involved in the handling of pesticides products must have the necessary accreditations for their handling and use.
- At the end of cultivation, if we have had incidence of disease and/or pests, it is recommended to disinfect the spent mushroom substrate before emptying the room.
- At the end of cultivation and with the room empty, perform a proper cleaning and disinfection cycle of the room to eliminate any possible remaining pathogens.
- Special attention should also be paid to the cleaning and disinfection of all material involved in mushroom cultivation: boxes, cultivation trolleys, knives, etc.
- It is recommended that from time to time, workers should renew their training related to cultivation, diseases, pests and phytosanitary products. In this way, they will be up to date with any new developments in these areas.
- Point out the different work areas, remembering the clothes (gloves, hats) that need to be worn to access the area.

About BIOSCHAMP and this Practice Abstract

This practice abstract was elaborated in the **BIOSCHAMP** project, based on the EIP AGRI practice abstract format. © 2024

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Goal: develop an integrated approach to tackle the mushroom cultivation challenges, improving the mushroom sector industrial profitability while reducing the agronomical need for pesticides by 90 %.